

Team assembly approach based in social modelling*

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Abstract

Team assembly is an important issue when collaborative or cooperative activities between people are carried out. In the educational context, it seems relevant to us to consider in the assembly process how students interact with others. Therefore, it is appropriate to carry out a process to model social behavior. In turn, the experts will be able to use the modeling information to establish the appropriate criteria to differentiate between assembly strategies according to the educational contexts. Our social behavior modeling process proposal is based on the information that can be extracted from the interactions and is guided by experts. We propose an approach divides into steps. Firstly, social network analysis metrics are used to study students' social interactions. Secondly, a set of social interactions attributes are offered so that experts can organize them hierarchically. Thirdly a quantitative information on the students' relationship that an influence diagram can infer due to the attributes hierarchically ordered. Once the modelling process is out, the qualitative information may be used to improve the team assembly. We describe in this paper two experiences where we have put it into practice our approach. The students made a peer review task. However, the pedagogical strategies that experts followed were different for each experience.

Keywords: Team assembly, Social Network Analysis, Social modelling, Influence diagrams, Teacher support.

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1 Introduction

Nowadays, online education is increasingly common and it allows the possibility to learn anywhere and anytime. One of the difficulties of online education can be the lack of interactions among students, although several pedagogical strategies encourage cooperation and collaboration (Barkley et al., 2004). When teachers or tutors proposes a cooperative or collaborative learning task, a small team of students should be created so that they can easily work together.

It is a critical challenge to decide who would be the most appropriate team members who could successfully work together to achieve the team goal (Gómez-Zar4 et al., 2020). Forming a group that effectively collaborates in a learning environment is one of the most challenging tasks in computer-supported collaborative learning (CSCL) (Maqtary et al., 2020). CSCL is a pedagogical approach that leverages networking technologies to facilitate social and instructional interactions among learners in small groups and learning communities. In addition, choosing a good group assembly strategy in an educational context is an open research area (Alberola et al., 2016a; Cruz & Isotani, 2014). As Cruz & Isotani (2014) pointed out, several studies have focused on developing and testing group assembly in collaborative learning contexts, but there is a lack of understanding of what techniques could help achieve a more effective group assembly from a pedagogical and dynamic perspective of the activity in the course.

It seems that a team assembly strategy should consider how the students interact with others because, as Saqr et al. (2018b,a), Al-Dhanhani et al. (2015) and Cho et al. (2007) pointed out, relationships among students can be used to observe and assess how the collaborative learning is taking place. According to Liu et al. (2018), there is evidence on the relationship between the characteristics of students' social network and their learning outcomes. The social characteristics of the student should be used to group students according to criteria appropriate to the learning context (G3mez-Zar4 et al., 2020).

It is relevant to us that the team assembly could be based on a students social behavior modeling and be guided by experts' criteria. The students generate a quite information when they interact with others in an online environment. The interactions can be used to analyzed the students' behaviour (Anaya & Boticario, 2011). The experts' criteria can tell apart among different assembly strategies or educational contexts. So, we point out the motivations of our research are: (1) to model the students social behaviour thanks to their interactions in social service; (2) to support teachers and tutors with the possibility of establishing specific criteria, using the students' social model, to assemble according to a specific educational context. The following research questions have guided our approach:

- RQ-1: How the student social behavior can be modeled quantitatively in a student's social model?
- RQ-2: What attributes can be used in the student's social model?
- RQ-3: How can the experts, teachers and tutors use the student's

social model to refine the assembly process?

- RQ-4: Can the proposed approach be applied in different educational contexts and can it be adapted to different experts' criteria?

The objective of the research presented in this work has been to offer the teacher an approach to assemble students for different educational contexts. Our proposal can model the students social behavior: 1) it uses social network analysis (SNA) (Saqr et al., 2018b,a) and quantitative techniques to study the relations among students in the conversations in the forums of an online course; 2) it offers teachers the possibility of establishing their own criteria that should be considered by the team assembly process; 3) it quantitatively assesses, based on an influence diagram (ID) (Howard & Matheson, 1984), the social relationship of each student with their classmates. Finally, an optimization procedure uses that information to find the best team assembly across the entire group of the students in the course. We have used our approach in two peer assessment experiences, where two different teachers used different criteria to guide the assembly process. The results obtained in these experiences constitute an initial validation of our approach and illustrate the flexibility of our proposal.

The paper is structured as follows. In the next section we present the state of the art of our research. In Section 3 we describe the approach in depth. To test the approach we have carried out two experiences that we explain in Section 4. We present the main research findings in Section 5. Finally, we briefly discuss our conclusions and plans for future work.

2 State of the art

2.1 Student team or group assembly

Recently, several researchers have focused on studying team assembly problems and have offered solutions, taxonomies, or strategies to solve them depending on the context (Gómez-Zar4 et al., 2020; Alberola et al., 2016a; Agrawal et al., 2014). Traditionally, the teachers' or tutors' duty is to decide how many individual groups are needed and the maximum number of students within each formal group for collaboration purposes (Stephens & Roberts, 2017). Cela et al. (2015a) pointed out that taking into account student preferences in the team assembly process, instead of doing it randomly, can increase the number of students who participate in discussions. Alternatively, Revelo-S4nchez et al. (2021) suggested forming collaborative groups based on homogeneous personality traits, a method shown to positively influence collaborative learning Sanz-Mart4nez et al., 2017.

G4mez-Zar4 et al. (2020) proposed a team assembly taxonomy that integrates two dimensions and four types. The two dimensions are: (1) users' agency and (2) users' participation. The four types are: *self-assembled teams*, where users organize their own teams; *staffed teams*, where a user customizes the equipment assembly criteria used by the system to simulate and form teams; *optimized teams*, where a system assem-

bles given particular team formation criteria; *augmented teams*, where the system augments user actions by suggesting potential teammates.

Cruz & Isotani (2014) studied team assembly area to identify the most common computational techniques: probabilistic algorithms (e.g., genetic and swarm intelligence algorithms), data mining techniques (e.g., k-means), and multi-agent approaches. Furthermore, artificial intelligence techniques are used to optimize teams when many factors are considered in team performance and assembly in an educational context (Alberola et al., 2016b).

The characteristics of the educational context that this research contemplates involve the student behavior in a social context. SNA techniques are generally used for that purpose (Saqr et al., 2018b,a). The next section gives more details about it.

2.1.1 Social network analysis in e-learning

SNA is the process of studying the structure of relationships among people through networks and graph theory. SNA has been extensively used in business, economics, and medicine. Nowadays it is becoming increasingly popular in an e-learning context (see, for example, De-Marcos et al., 2016, Cela et al., 2015b). (see, for example, Vallejo et al. (2009), De-Marcos et al. (2016), Oshima et al. (2013), Cela et al. (2015a)). It is important to note that Vallejo et al. (2009) consider the social dynamics of interaction between the actors of the learning activity through SNA in order to analyze, monitor and finally help strengthen the dynamics of interaction present in the activities CSCL. In addition, Oshima et al. (2013) also focus on interactions among learners but in a face-to-face context, exchanging ideas between turns of conversation. In the educational context, a social network can be built where the nodes are the participants (students, teachers, tutors, etc.) and the edges connecting the nodes (ties or links) indicate relationships or interactions. There are various factors (i.e.: social characteristics, motivational models, recommender systems) that the social networks could incorporate to foster student collaboration (Al-Dhanhani et al., 2015). Nevertheless SNA has been used to identify students' social characteristics due to the relationship between SNA metrics and the students performance in the network. For instance, Saqr et al. (2018b,a) have researched the specific relation between the metrics and the students behavior for teachers to monitor students in the online course. A more general approach to this issue is by (Saxena et al., 2019). These authors have surveyed the papers in the area and have proposed a set of SNA metrics to characterize individuals and networks as a whole. In the educational context, the forums are the primary means to connect the participants and are the main source to build the networks to do the SNA (Saqr et al., 2020). The relationship between students' outcomes and their SNA metrics have been shown (Saqr et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2018).

2.1.2 Matching reviewers

Peer review can be considered as a cooperative task and matching reviewers can be considered as team assembly. However, matching reviewers

process is rarely discussed in the literature. The reviewers are teammates with an specific role in a peer review task. Topping (1998) and Crespo-García et al. (2005) are two of the few authors that discuss this question. A random assignment method is the most common process to assign reviewers.

Crespo-García et al. (2005) describe an algorithm for matching reviewers to group students according to their profiles in a peer review context. More precisely, an algorithm for matching reviewers depending on the students characteristics in the educational peer review process, generates the pairs according to a given pedagogical criterion. In this line, Capuano & Caballé (2015) also propose a procedure based on students' past grades in previous peer assessment tasks. Another approach is by Piech et al. (2013) that considered dividing peer graders into language groups (English and Spanish) to address concerns of being graded by a non-native speaker as well as the observed "patriotic grading effect", and Gehringer (2001) considered groups of students working on the same project or topic.

2.2 Probabilistic graphical models

Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGMs) (Koller & Friedman, 2009) were developed by Artificial Intelligence researchers for the purpose of solving problems that have uncertainty. Bayesian networks (BNs) (Pearl, 1988) constitute a modeling framework where cause-effect and probabilistic dependence and independence relationships are easily represented. BNs allow easy communication with the expert when the model is being built and debugged (Lacave & Díez, 2002).

IDs (Howard & Matheson, 1984, 2005) are an extension of BNs that include decision variables and the quantification of the decision maker's preferences. IDs allow the expert not only to carry out diagnostic tasks as in BNs, but they also offer very interesting possibilities (Bielza et al., 2011; Anaya et al., 2013): (1) know which is the best action in each scenario (Nielsen & Jensen, 1999; Luque et al., 2017), (2) obtain automatically explanations of the reasoning of the system (Lacave et al., 2007), and (3) formulate queries about the posterior probabilities and the expected utilities of the model variables (Luque & Díez, 2006).

In the original ID framework (Howard & Matheson, 1984), all utility nodes in the ID are assumed to be combined together with an implicit sum (Jensen & Nielsen, 2007). Tatman & Shachter (1990) extended IDs to allow for a special type of utility node, called a *super-value*, that can combine (by sum or product) the utility functions of other nodes. The possibility of nesting super-value nodes provides great flexibility to the decision maker when it comes to representing the structure of the model (Luque & Díez, 2010) and improves the efficiency of the inference algorithm that computes the optimal strategy.

PGMs have previously been used in the educational context. BNs have been applied to student modeling (Conati et al., 1997, 2002; Millán & Pérez-De-La-Cruz, 2002; Millán et al., 2010; Reye, 1996), in some cases focused on learning styles (García et al., 2007) or identification of the level of knowledge (Mislevy & Gitomer, 1996). Chang (2003) proposed a courseware diagram method based on an ID to help an instructor design

the structure of a course composed of instructional material and online tests. IDs have also been used to build a recommender system in a collaborative learning environment (Anaya et al., 2013; Anaya & Luque, 2013), allowing the use of graphical explanation capabilities based on induction decision trees (Anaya et al., 2016).

3 Building a model for the Student-Student relationship

We propose a flexible approach to quantitatively measure the relationship among students. We highlight the importance of the social characteristics of the students in the team assembly process (Gómez-Zar4 et al., 2020). However, different educational contexts or different cooperative or collaborative tasks may guide different appropriate decisions to assemble students. We do not propose a specific pedagogical strategy, but rather a flexible framework.

3.1 Structure

Figure 1 summarizes our approach. First of all, the educational context must offer a communication service so that the participants can interact with each other. Usually the most common communication service in the educational context are forums, which have been the focus of several researchers to obtain indicators of student actions (Daradoumis et al., 2010). The proposed approach used only the interactions in forums. Secondly, forums communications and interactions are translated into a machine-readable language. Thirdly, an SNA is performed to measure a set of attributes to quantify the social behavior of the participants. Fourthly, an expert specifies the criteria to choose the most suitable candidate keeping in mind the attributes. Fifthly, the inference tool based on an ID incorporates in a flexible way two different sources of information: (1) the attributes (quantitative, probabilistic, and related to direct interaction) that can explain the student social behavior and (2) the expert criteria. The output of the ID is a utility table that quantifies the quality of each student in the team assembly process.

3.2 Student social behavior attributes and the Social Network Analysis

It is not the objective of this paper to discuss the individual characteristics of people that can describe their social behavior (Blass, 2015). Instead, we have focused on the information about the students interactions that can be obtained from the main communication services in an e-learning environment. The main communication service in a Learning Management System are the forums, which can be analyzed by SNA (Liu et al., 2018). We have classified the information into three attributes types: (1) quantitative information about the student social behavior; (2) qualitative information about the student social behavior; (3) information about

Figure 1: General schema of the approach.

the individual relation student to student.

3.2.1 Quantitative information about the student's social behavior

According to Saqr et al. (2020), SNA can perform two levels of analysis in a learning context: 1) the individual user level to calculate user activity metrics that reflect the quantity of interactions as well as variables that reflect the user's position and role in information exchange (Liao et al., 2017; Borgatti, 2005); 2) the group network level, so the properties of the interaction network can reveal important insights that can help teachers and learning designers.

At the individual user level we have proposed the following metrics, which were explained in depth in our previous research (Anaya et al., 2019): the number of conversations that a student has started (*Initiative*); the number of messages that a student has sent (*Messages*); the number of replies to messages sent by a student (*Popularity*); Closeness centrality (*Closeness*); Betweenness centrality (*Betweenness*); Eigenvector centrality (*Eigenvector*).

At the group network level, we have proposed the metric *Modularity*, which describes the topological structure of the network and can identify its connected components (Rodríguez-Hidalgo et al., 2015). The modularity structure classifies nodes into groups, where within a group nodes are highly connected, and across groups nodes are loosely connected (Chakraborty et al., 2017; Girvan & Newman, 2002). Modularity can inform the teacher about the closest students even if they are not directly

connected to each other.

3.2.2 Qualitative information about the student's social behavior

There are attributes or categories, which describe the students, that can not be measured quantitatively due to the attributes or categories nature (Rosch, 1978). We can categorize a person as old or young by knowing their exact age. However, we cannot know if a student is good or bad, or active or passive, knowing only a quantitative attribute. It would be necessary to have much more information, which is not always possible, to eliminate uncertainty in the categorization. PGMs are very well suited to be applied in contexts that have uncertainty, that is, situations in which there is not complete conviction or knowledge about the outcome or result of a variable.

In this research, although we have recorded the number of messages sent by each student, it is reasonable to think that other indicators can also influence the level of activity of a student by providing relevant information. We propose to solve this issue by using a qualitative categorization of the student activity in the three levels in the attribute *Activity*: high, medium, low.

3.2.3 Information about the individual relation student to student

We have considered only the number of messages that one student sent to other as a quantification of the students relationship. We have named this attribute *SharedMessages*.

3.3 Teacher role in the approach or Teacher's criteria of assignment

The teacher role remains decisive in setting the learning aims and objectives, exploiting different teaching approaches and strategies, and determining how to apply technologies (Klimova, 2016). The use of the Information and communications technology can facilitate to teachers and tutors the teaching process and, thus, the learning process (Nikolić et al., 2019). For these reasons, our approach is teacher-centered. Teachers or tutors can manage and establish the team assembly strategy, what they consider the most appropriate in the educational context.

Our approach offers teachers and tutors an understandable strategy to guide the inference process so that the approach can be adapted to the experts' or tutors' pedagogical strategy. Therefore, the teacher and tutors can rank the attributes. The attributes are pointed out in the previous section and listed here:

- Quantitative:
 - We represent the students social attributes with the following variables: *Popularity*, *Eigenvector*, *Betweenness*, *Initiative*, and *Closeness*.

- We represent the topological structure of the network with the attribute *Modularity*, which indicates the membership of the student to a group of related students.
- Qualitative:
 - We define the variable *ActivityCompatibility* to account for the compatibility between the activity of the students.
- Student-to-student relationship:
 - We determine whether two students have contacted each other using the attribute *SharedMessages*, which is a numeric variable with a value equal to the number of messages exchanged between the two students.

Experts or tutors can arrange these attributes in the most appropriate order according to their opinion.

3.4 Probabilistic graphical model built for the approach

In the particular case of the educational context in the collaboration problem, there is uncertainty around the variables that influence student collaboration (Rosch, 1978). In this research, although we have recorded the number of messages sent by each student, it is reasonable to think that other indicators can also influence the level of activity of a student by providing relevant information. Unfortunately, there is uncertainty around such indicators. Thus, a PGM could deal well with this situation. A Bayesian network (BN) (Jensen & Nielsen, 2007) would be enough, but, in our case, we want to evaluate the expected utility of each potential team mate in a team assembly process. Thus, as an extension of a BN, an ID (Howard & Matheson, 1984) fulfills our purpose. IDs provide a decision support framework that, based on a compact representation, facilitates the elicitation of numerical parameters and helps the knowledge engineer easily explain the model to the domain expert (in our case, the tutor) (Lacave et al., 2007). Moreover, the ID extension provided by super-value nodes (Tatman & Shachter, 1990) can help to simplify the representation of the utility function if in our case we use a weighted linear combination (Steuer, 1986) from the criteria previously ordered by the expert.

We have separated the construction of an ID model: first, the quantitative part, i.e., the structure, and second, the quantitative part, i.e., the numerical parameters.

3.4.1 Structure of the influence diagram

We start describing how we have built the structure of the ID. For the figures that we attach in this section to explain the process of construction, we have followed the convention of representation of the types of nodes followed in most of the ID literature and software packages. Thus, *chance* nodes, which correspond to uncertain events, are represented by yellow ovals. *Utility* nodes, which correspond to the quantification of the decision maker's preferences, are represented by green diamonds (hexagons).

Figure 2: Graph structure of the Quantitative information about the student social behavior, “Attributes”.

The utility function in an ID allows the user to specify the quantification of the decision maker preferences. The graph of an ID needs to give insight about the structure of that quantification. In relation to this issue, in Figures 2, 3 and 4 we have also used the same semantics for arcs used in IDs literature. Thus, the arcs towards a utility node indicates the domain of the corresponding utility function. For example, in Figure 3, the utility of *Activity Compatibility* functionally depends on the *Activity* of the two students (but not on any other nodes). The arcs towards a chance node indicate the existence of a probability function conditioned on the parents in the graph. For example, in Figure 2, a probability function associated to each node of *Activity* depends on each *Student*.

By following the description of attributes defined in Section 3.3, we have first represented a weighted linear combination of the quantitative attributes *Popularity*, *Eigenvector*, *Betweenness*, *Initiative*, and *Closeness*. The general scheme of this combination is presented in Figure 2. Inside each *Attribute* utility node a product is executed taking as input the corresponding *Weight*. Each arch from an *Attribute* utility node to the node *Utility* indicates that the corresponding attribute contributes as an addend in the function of the node *Utility*.

To analyze the activity compatibility of each pair of students, the ID has a representation as in Figure 3. Nodes *Student 1* and *Student 2* represent the two students whose activity compatibility is going to be analyzed, and each one has associated an *Activity* node as a child in the graph. The *Activity Compatibility* node have as parents the nodes of *Activity* of the two students. We will see in a subsequent section how the expert defines numerically this function. The utility node *Activity Compatibility* is parent of the node *Utility* because it contributes to the global expected utility of the ID; it also has associated a weight, as the quantitative attributes defined in Section 3.3, but it has not been explicitly drawn in Figure 3 for simplification purposes.

To incorporate the influence of the shared messages between each pair of students, the ID has represented a structure as in Figure 4. The utility

Figure 3: Graph structure of the Qualitative information about the student social behavior, “Activity compatibility”.

Figure 4: Graph structure of the information about the individual relation student to student, “Shared messages”.

function of *Shared Messages* depends on the two students (nodes *Student 1* and *Student 2*) and a *Weight* used in the linear combination in the function of the *Utility* node.

3.4.2 Numerical parameters

To have a full implementation of the ID, we need to elicit the numerical values corresponding to the probability and utility parameters. By refining the scheme of elicitation used by (Anaya et al., 2019), we propose a more sophisticated approach by partitioning the set of numerical parameters into three sets:

1. Those parameters that are taken from expert knowledge and that do not depend on the course to which the model is applied. These parameters are elicited by a knowledge engineer.
2. Those parameters that depend on the course to which the model is applied but that are automatically elicited by a computational system; in this case they are calculated via the SNA of the students in the course being considered.
3. Those parameters that depend on the course to which the model is applied but that are manually elicited by the teacher or the tutor of

the course, who has extra knowledge about the peculiarities of the course and its group of the students.

As Anaya et al. (2019) did, we have built an *ID template* by eliciting only the parameters in set (1), which therefore can be easily adapted to any other course by eliciting only the parameters in sets (2) and (3). This template helps to avoid elicitation errors when the ID is used in different educational contexts.

The distinction between sets (2) and (3) try to illustrate that we have tried to automate as much as possible the elicitation of parameters, thus trying to save time and effort to the expert (the teacher or the tutor). These two sets will be explained in the corresponding experimentation of each course.

Numerical parameters in the ID template (set 1) Eliciting the numerical parameters of the ID template, i.e., those in the set (1), only required a minimal setup of probability parameters.

To elicit the probability table of each *Activity* chance node, we have used the same table as in (Anaya et al., 2019). These authors use numerical parameters that indicate that there is a high probability, 0.7, that the *Activity* is determined by the number of messages sent by the student, but because this probability is not 1.0, the table reflects that other factors can also influence the *Activity*, so we have uncertainty about that.

As in (Anaya et al., 2019), the probability tables of the nodes *Student 1* and *Student 2* are irrelevant as long as they assign a non-zero probability to each student. Thus, we have assigned a discrete uniform distribution to the probability functions of these two nodes.

Completing the elicitation of the numerical parameters for a specific course (sets 2 and 3) Numerical parameters in the set (2) have been automatically elicited as in (Anaya et al., 2019). In this way, the number of messages sent by each student was first counted, and then each value was discretized into one of the following three values: *low*, *medium* and *high*. For this, an equal frequency binning method was used.

Parameters in the set (3) depend on the course to which the model is applied and are manually elicited. The utility table of the node *Activity Compatibility* contains nine parameters, but only six of them are independent and must be elicited. To elicit the weights of the utility nodes of the qualitative attributes and the *Shared Messages* node we used the ordering of criteria provided by the expert, and then for an attribute in the i -th position in the ordering we assigned a weight proportional to i^2 .¹

3.4.3 Computation of the expected utility table

The main objective of building the ID model is to obtain the expected utility table (see Figure 1). This table, denoted as *EU*, provides for each pair of students r and s how appropriate is to evaluate how appropriate is the student s for a team assembly task with student r . We must note

¹Anaya et al. (2019) also tested other increasing monotonic functions of i , like $f(i) = i$, and $f(i) = \sqrt{i}$, but $f(i) = i^2$ provided better results.

that this relation does not be in general symmetric, i.e., we have no guarantee that $EU(r, s) = EU(s, r)$.

The table EU can be calculated with OpenMarkov (Arias & Díez, 2008; Arias et al., 2019; Díez et al., 2022), an open-source tool for probabilistic graphical models available at www.openmarkov.org. For these computations OpenMarkov only needs as input the ID model, including the graph (nodes and edges) and the numerical parameters.

The table EU acts as basis for any posterior analysis that tries to optimize the team assembly process across the entire course. For example, Anaya et al. (2019) implemented an algorithm for assigning reviewers to each student based on EU that outperformed a random assignment. We used their implementation in this paper.

4 Experimentation

We can sum up: our approach’s results are a student’s relation table. The values in the table values quantify the relation of each students with their mates according to some attributes and criteria. The attributes are related to the social student behaviour (see Section 3.2), and the criteria are an order of the attributes importance (see Section 3.3). The ID offers the utility matrix which means the student relation table.

Our objective was to test the utility and flexibility of the proposed approach. Therefore, we made two experiment cases: *Case 1*, where the participation in an OPA task was optional. The teacher’s criteria were the pair reviewer-student had had a maximal social relation to increase the participation. *Case 2*, where the participation in the OPA task was mandatory. The teacher’s criteria were the pair reviewer-student had had a minimal social relation to increase the impartiality.

Revelo-Sánchez et al. (2021) point out that group formation is very important when developing activities in collaborative learning contexts. This is due to the fact it is not sufficient just putting learners in group and telling them to work together (Collazos et al., 2003), so it is desired to “increase collaboration in order to achieve group cognition” (Stahl, 2006). For that reason, the Case 1 was based in the social connection established in the forum. It is important to mention that OPA tasks improve learning and encourage social interactions in a distance education environment (Uto & Ueno, 2016) although it is known that there may be a lack of commitment and participation by the students on it (Meek et al., 2016). For that reason, Anaya et al. (2019) developed a social analysis-based reviewer assignment method for use in OPA tasks. Later in our present article it will be seen that the students themselves expressed their satisfaction with the formation of the groups, so it can be said that the above strategy has taken into consideration the importance of forming “good” groups according to Revelo-Sánchez et al. (2021). Additionally, in the Case 1 we pursue forming homogeneous as in Revelo-Sánchez et al. (2021). It is worth mentioning that we have not used variables such as gender, age or culture to keep our proposal as least intrusive as possible.

Table 1: Utility table of ActivityCompatibility for case 1.

StudentActivity	ReviewerActivity		
	high	medium	low
high	0.6	0.2	0.2
medium	0.2	0.6	0.2
low	0.2	0.2	0.6

4.1 Case 1

This case corresponds to the same subject “Complexity and Computability” used by Anaya et al. (2019) although in the 2019/2020 edition. The differences with the edition used in the previous paper was a modification of the way of interacting in Twitter being once a week with six true/false questions instead of daily and give the students the opportunity of answering them all the whole week. Additionally, it was introduced a connection between Twitter and the LMS, in the sense that the wrongly answered questions in Twitter were discussed in the forum. These modifications eased the participation of the students in the LMS. Another modification of this edition was related to the criteria preferences that will be described below. The rest of the experience was the same: conducting an OPA task around the recording of a modular teaching mini-video or MTM (see Letón & Molanes-López, 2014; Luzón & Letón, 2015; Letón et al., 2018; Rodríguez-Ascaso et al., 2018 for a detailed description of the characteristics of an MTM and their benefits in learning).

4.1.1 Experts’ criteria

In this case 1, the OPA task was not mandatory, and gave to the students the possibility of getting 0.6 extra points. The motivation for choosing the reviewer and the one revised was to have a great social connection between them, following the homophily effect in line with the proverb "birds of a feather flock together" (see, for example, McPherson et al., 2001 and Stepanyan et al., 2010). For this reason, it is important that both students share activity and modularity. In addition, the following ranking was proposed: ActivityCompatibility > shared messages > modularity > closenesscentrality > Initiative > betweennesscentrality > eigencentality > Popularity.

The utility table for ActivityCompatibility was instantiated as it is shown in Table 1. In Section 4.2.1 we explain the differences between this table and the one used in case 2, reflecting different perspectives from the experts’ point of view.

4.1.2 Assignment results

We divided the students who recorded MTMs and participated in the forum into an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group was formed by students whose forum interactions were analysed and

the control group by those where forum interactions were not analysed. Additionally, we considered a third group (called others) formed by those who recorded an MTM but did not participated in the forum or did not record an MTM, in order to give the opportunity of participating to all the students.

4.1.3 Student opinion

After the students finished the OPA task, they had to fill out a very simple questionnaire with three questions about the task:

- Question 1: How much time in minutes did this activity take you in total? This question had 49 answers that supplied that the median time needed for carrying out the activity was 45 minutes.
- Question 2: Did you find this activity useful? This question had 49 answers which means that 100% of the students who filled the questionnaire found the activity useful.
- Question 3: Overall comments you want to make about peer review of MTMs. This question had 38 answers which means that 78% of the students who filled the questionnaire have spontaneously expressed comments about the activity. Besides, all of these comments were positive. The main comments about the OPA task were that the activity was useful to review concepts and that the students were delighted with it because in a fun way they collaborate and learn among them.

4.2 Case 2

This case corresponds to the subject “Social Media Mining” in the 2019/2020 edition. Due to the exceptional situation of COVID-19, the presently final exam was replaced by an OPA task. In this task the student had to review the last continuous assessment practice task done by two course mates. In addition to review the work by course mates, the student had to propose improvements and do one of them. The OPA task in this case was mandatory.

4.2.1 Experts’ criteria

The motivation of the teacher was to avoid having the couple of students, one reviewer and the other reviewed, having many communications between them so that the review was as impartial as possible. For this reason, two important changes were proposed with respect to the criteria in case 1:

- students should have different activity level;
- and that students who do not share the same modularity class.

In addition, the following ranking was proposed: ActivityCompatibility > modularity > Initiative > eigencentality > betweennesscentrality > closenesscentrality > Popularity > shared messages.

Table 2: Utility table of ActivityCompatibility for case 2.

StudentActivity	ReviewerActivity		
	high	medium	low
high	0.2	0.4	0.4
medium	0.4	0.2	0.4
low	0.4	0.4	0.2

Table 3: Assignment table for Case 2.

	1(6)	2(5)	3(8)	4(2)	5(4)	6(3)	7(7)	8(9)
1(6)		61	62	68	38	31	33	46
2(5)	64		50	58	23	41	48	34
3(8)	64	48		58	25	42	47	32
4(2)	62	49	50		26	43	45	34
5(4)	64	47	50	58		41	48	34
6(3)	52	59	62	70	35		36	46
7(7)	51	61	62	68	38	31		46
8(9)	64	48	48	58	25	42	47	

So that the ActivityCompatibility attribute had a opposite importance than in case 1, the utility table for ActivityCompatibility was instantiated newly:

Table 1 and 2 show differences due to the experts' strategies. In the case 1 the experts considered important that great social connection between reviewer and the other reviewed, and their activity could be compatible. Then, in Table 1 the diagonal has the higher values. In the case 2, oppositely, the motivation was impartial of review. The reviewer and the other reviewed should have few connections, and their activity could be incompatible. So, in Table 2 the diagonal has the lower values.

4.2.2 Assignment results

Our approach offered a table with the proposed assignation for all the students according to a quadratic distribution of the weights. The quadratic distribution gave the most appropriate way to maximize the whole utility in or previous research (Anaya et al., 2019). Table 3 shows the utility of the assignation as reviewer for all the students. The green color points out the optimum reviewer and the lilac color the possible reviewer due to others, more appropriate, were assign to other students. The Table 3 corresponds to the Student's Relation Table in Figure 1.

4.2.3 Student opinion

After the OPA task was finished, the students were able to answer a small questionnaire to know their opinions about the OPA task, the assignation and the subject. The questionnaire had four straight questions and six

students answered. The first and second question asked about the OPA task:

- Question 1: Did you find the OPA task appropriate as an assessment approach for the subject? Two students answered that very appropriate and four appropriate.
- Question 2: Do you think that in the OPA task you have demonstrated your knowledge about the concepts taught in this subject?. Six students answered that appropriately.

The third and fourth questions asked about the assignation:

- Question 3: What do you think of the assignment of the works to review? One student answered that very good assignation and five good assignation.
- Question 4: As a participant in the OPA task, how the assignment approach has been for you? Four students answered that appropriate and two indifferent.

We can conclude that the students' opinion were favorable or very favorable to the OPA task and the assignment approach.

5 Discussion

In the online education the cooperation and collaboration task manage should be based on the information that the system has about the student (Johnson & Young, 2011), that is, the student model (Kay & Kummerfeld, 2019; Bull, 2020). Our research has focused on students team assembly based on modeling the student's social behavior.

In the Introduction we proposed four research questions. In this section we ask them.

- RQ-1: How the student social behavior can be modeled quantitatively in a student's social model? The student model can manage and store different students attributes, as students' evaluations or features (Kay & Kummerfeld, 2019). However, our approach have used the information that SNA can offer, because of the usefulness (Saqr et al., 2018b,a) and we point out that these information can obtain Students' social information easily in a common e-learning context (Saqr et al., 2020).
- RQ-2: What attributes can be used in the student's social model? We have divided the students' social information into three categories: quantitative attributes; qualitative attributes; attributes about the individual relation student to student. We have proposes the categorization so that teachers and tutor can understand easily the students' social model.
- RQ-3: How can the experts, teachers and tutors use the student's social model to refine the assembly process? For us it is very important that the teachers and tutor can participate in the manage process of the students' social model and the students relation with each other. The easiness and understandably can play an important

role (Bull & Kay, 2010). We have proposed that experts' criteria are taken into account to build a model for student-student relationship so that our approach can be adapted to different contexts and sensibilities. To obtain this objective our approach have used an ID, which offers flexibility and uncertainty manage (Nielsen et al., 2007). The ID, in the way that we have used, can calculate the student-student relationship using the student's social model and the experts' criteria. Then, the student-student relationship can be used to assemble students teams.

- RQ-4: Can the proposed approach be applied in different educational contexts and can it adapt to different experts' criteria? We have proposed two experimentation cases to test our approach. The experimentation cases consisted in a OPA task where our approach assigned reviewers for an student work In the experimentation cases the experts' criteria followed different pedagogical scenes. The students considered the assignation enough appropriate. Different criteria, due to the different pedagogical scenes, have been used and the outcomes has been similar.

In Section 3.4.2 we noted that we have refined the numerical parameter elicitation scheme used by Anaya et al. (2019), so we propose a more sophisticated approach by partitioning the set of numerical parameters into three sets instead of just two. This difference comes from the fact that we have partitioned the set of parameters that the expert must obtain manually into what in Section 3.4.2 we call sets 1 and 3. We made this partition because in set 1 we arrange the numerical parameters whose value that can be considered not dependent on the course to which the model is applied. In contrast, parameters in set 3 are manually elicited by the teacher or the tutor of the course and can therefore incorporate additional insights that consider the specific e-learning context of the students and the course. In synthesis, in this research we have tried to advance into a framework that not factorizes the model to improve its flexibility improve while maintaining a compact and efficient representation and implementation of the model, involving the expert in the elicitation of parameters that can be key in the assembly of teams. We believe that her participation is very important so that she can better accept the recommendation of an artificial system like the one proposed in this research.

6 Conclusion and future works

We have proposed an approach to assemble students team in a socio-educational context. The principal part of the approach in the process to measure the relation student-student quantitatively according the students social behavior and the expert's criteria. This information can be used to ensemble students groups. In this paper describe in depth the approach and we have described two OPA task experiences where the expert's criteria was different and had different pedagogical objectives. Thus, we have tested the usefulness and flexibility of our approach. According the students answers the approach can be used in different educational context.

In our approach we use only information about the students behavior in a social context. One of the future improvements should be insertion of the students individual action information in the model. In this way, the students previous assessments can be used. We have not performed any textual analysis of the messages sent by students. Natural language analysis could give information about the quality of the student-student relationships, for example thanking of Sentiment Analysis. This is an improvement that we should develop in future versions of our approach. In addition, we have tested the approach in a peer-review tasks. We claim that our approach can be used in other educational contexts, as MOOCs, and in a other collaborative task as a team work. Therefore, we should apply the approach in these different educational contexts.

Declarations

Conflict of interest The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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